

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP4 – Establishment of a non-commercial, Europe-wide breast milk biobank and analytical centre

D4.8 Standard documents for pre-examination processes for breast milk handling and Guideline for Biobanking

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Abstract

As part of ConcePTION WP4, D4.8, the partners have developed standard documents for pre-examination processes for the handling of breast milk and blood sampling at the clinical site and at the participants' homes. All documents meet ethical, legal and regulatory requirements based on European and International Standards for biobanking and pre-analytical sample handling (ISO 20387 - General Requirements for biobanking, ISO 9001 - Quality Management Systems requirements, ISO 20186 - Specifications for pre-examination processes for venous whole blood) as well as following the guideline for good clinical practice E6 (R2), ICH-GCP for the protection of donor rights and safety.

These standard documents were used in the demonstration projects (task 4.3) measuring selected medications in breast milk and maternal blood/plasma and assessing exposure of breastfed infants will be performed, which will provide evidence for appropriate methodology for different chemical classes. The selected medication in the demonstration studies have been amoxicillin, levocetirizine, metformin, prednisolone and venlafaxine. Standardised protocols for determination of concentrations of the selected drugs and their metabolites in breast milk and plasma have been applied in all demonstration studies and have been subject to validated methods for determination of drugs in the biological matrices such as plasma and breast milk samples. The samples were stored in the Uppsala Biobank.

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1. Introduction

In the Framework of ConcePTION five demonstration (observational) studies have been carried out, investigating the effects of medicines (amoxicillin, levocetirizine, metformin, prednisolone and venlafaxine) taken during pregnancy and breastfeeding to help women make informed decisions about taking medicines before, during and after pregnancy.

When collecting human biospecimens and associated data it is mandatory to adhere to ethical, legal and regulatory requirements (chapter 2). The investigator-driven demonstration studies performed within ConcePTION have been set up according to standardised protocols.

All the protocols have been approved by appropriate ethical review boards and regulatory authorities and registered at EU-PAS displayed in the HMA-EMA Catalogues (subchapter 2.1), EudraCT (subchapter 2.2) and followed ICH-GCP requirements (subchapter 2.3).

Medication	Study title	Study Registration
Levocetirizine	Levocetirizine/cetirizine levels in human milk – an observational, clinical study among breastfeeding women. PI: Prof. Hedvig Nordeng, PharmaSafe, Pharmacoepidemiology and Drug Safety Research Group, Oslo, Norway	EUPAS 46213
Venlafaxine	Prediction of venlafaxine exposure through breastfeeding. PI: Prof. Alice Panchaud, CHUV Lausanne, Switzerland	EUPAS 103385
Amoxicillin	Evaluation of Amoxicillin diffusion in breast milk according to a population pharmacokinetic approach PI: Peggy Gandia, PharmD, PhD, CHU Toulouse, France	N°EudraCT 2021-002247-30
Metformin	Transfer of metformin into human breast milk and the plasma of breastfeeding children - A low intervention trial with biobanking of breast milk and plasma in Västra Götalandsregionen and Region Örebro PI: Prof. Mats Hansson, Uppsala University, Sweden	EUPAS 105190, CTIS 2022-501693-19-00
Prednisolone	Transfer of prednisolone into human breast milk and plasma of breastfeeding children - A low intervention cohort study with biobanking of breast milk and plasma. PI: Prof. Mats Hansson, Uppsala University, Sweden	EUPAS 1000000059, CTIS 2023-508913-18-00

Standard protocols have been established (chapter 3) and implemented in the four study sites/clinical sites UNIGE, CHUT, UOSL UPPS (chapter 4).

2. Ethical, legal and regulatory requirements

2.1 HMA-EMA Catalogues

The HMA-EMA Catalogues¹ displays real-world data sources and studies (former EU PAS Register) at the European Network of Centres for Pharmacoepidemiology and Pharmacovigilance (ENCePP) website², coordinated by the European Medicines Agency³.

2.2 EudraCT

EudraCT⁴ (European Union Drug Regulating Authorities Clinical Trials Database) is the database for all interventional clinical trials on medicinal products.

2.3 Good Clinical Practice

Good clinical practice⁵ (GCP) the international ethical and scientific quality standard for designing, recording, and reporting trials that involve the participation of human subjects. Compliance with this standard provides public assurance that the rights, safety and wellbeing of trial subjects are protected, and that clinical-trial data are credible.

3. Standard documents for pre-examination (pre-analytical) processes for breast milk handling and blood collection, applied in demonstration studies

3.1 Pre-analytical variables

Diverse factors may negatively affect biospecimen integrity and/or quality and, ultimately, research results. These factors are normally referred to as 'pre-analytical variables' (see

). Pre-analytical variables can be divided into three areas: (1) donor intrinsic physiological factors, (2) biospecimen collection (e.g., type of collection tube or container, timing, and intermediate transport and storage temperature), and (3) further sample processing and biobanking procedures (transport, processing time and temperature, storage, retrieval and distribution) prior its inclusion in any downstream applications.

Figure 1: Biospecimen handling pipeline (modified from Yeung et al.⁶): pre-analytical variables can affect various steps of the pipeline, from biospecimen collection to downstream analysis.

The most critical pre-analytical variables shall be tracked and monitored in a Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS) or Biobank Information Management System (BIMS) system. Documentation can be applied with a coding system (e.g., SPREC⁷ annotation), which is used in clinical sites and by various biobanks. Sample and data collection should always record the date and time, collection site, collection method and any deviations from protocols and/or standard operating procedures (SOPs) and anomalies (if applicable) to identify possible causes of unexpected analytical results caused by pre-analytical errors.

From 2008 to 2022, the FP7-funded SPIDIA project and its successor project SPIDIA4P⁸, a Horizon 2020 project of the European Union, developed a comprehensive portfolio of 19 European Preanalytical Standards (CEN/TS) and International Standards (ISO/IS) documents, as well as complementary External Quality Assessment Procedures (EQAs), addressing key preanalytical workflows in personalised medicine and representing a milestone for medical diagnostics, biomedical research and biobanking^{9,10}.

These series of standards on pre-analytical sample processing have been published by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO¹¹) and the European Committee for Standardization (CEN¹²) and support the COMMISSION RECOMMENDATION (EU) 2023/498 of 1 March 2023 on a Code of Practice on standardisation in the European Research Area¹³.

3.2 Standard Documents for pre-examination processes for breast milk handling

The following templates were developed in WP4 and served as standard operating documents in the demonstration studies and are attached to this report.

- 01_Template_Providing Information_Home_V1.0
- 02_Template_Providing Information_Clinic_V1.0
- 03_Template_Consent Form_V1.0
- 04_Template_Collection Milk_Clinic_V1.0
- 05_Template_Collection Milk_Home_V1.0
- 06_Template_Collection Blood_Clinic_V1.0

- 07_Template_Collection Blood_Home_V1.0
- 08_Template_Questionnaire_Breast Milk Sampling_Home_V1.0
- 09_Template_Questionnaire_Breast Milk Sampling_Clinic_V1.0
- 10_Template_Questionnaire_Blood Sampling Mother_V1.0
- 11_Template_Questionnaire_Blood Sampling_Personnel_V1.0
- 12_Work Instruction_Sample_Shipment_V1.0
- 13_Work Instruction_Sending_Encrypted_Data_V1.0
- 14_Work Instruction_Sample_Storage_V1.0

The documents listed above, which are essentially Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), can be found in the full version in the appendices.

4. Demonstration studies

4.1 General

Protocols for the demonstration studies were examined and approved by appropriate ethical review boards and regulatory authorities. Two were milk-only studies, one for levocetirizine with UOSL as leading partner, one for venlafaxine with ULAUS as leading partner. One study was Mothers milk and plasma study for amoxicillin with CHUT as leading partner. Two studies were Mother-Infant pair study for metformin and prednisolone with UPPS as leading partner.

For milk-only studies, collection of breast milk was conducted in the participant's homes utilising electric breast milk pumps to collect milk, with the milk sample then being shipped to Uppsala Biobank with courier. Mothers' milk and plasma as well as mother-infant studies required setting up and collaborating with clinical centres and regional biobanks based on approved protocols for clinical trials.

Recruitment was a challenge in particular for the metformin and prednisolone studies since plasma was to be collected also from the newborn infant.

4.2 Amoxicillin

The study pursued two objectives. The primary objective of this study is to characterise the pharmacokinetics of amoxicillin in lactating women through the development of a population pharmacokinetic model.

The primary model aims to:

- (i) delineate the kinetic profile of amoxicillin in breast milk and assess its variability;
- (ii) identify the factors contributing to this variability;
- (iii) predict the daily dose ingested by the infant and its variability across different maternal dosing regimens.

The secondary objectives include:

- (i) monitoring the occurrence of predefined adverse reactions in infants during lactation;
- (ii) evaluating the impact of amoxicillin consumption on breast milk production.

Material and Method

Blood and milk samples were collected from breastfeeding mothers who had been treated with amoxicillin for at least two days. The sampling involved:

- Three breast milk collections of approximately 20 ml each, using an electric breast pump provided to the participants;
- Three blood samples of approximately 5 ml each.

These samples were taken at the following time points:

- 15-30 minutes after amoxicillin intake,
- 1-2 hours post-intake,
- 3-4 hours post-intake.

To assess potential adverse effects of amoxicillin in infants, mothers were asked to complete a paper questionnaire on the day of sampling, followed by a telephone interview one week later.

Participants were required to be mothers over 18 years old, receiving oral amoxicillin alone or in combination with clavulanic acid, following a dosage regimen aligned with the Marketing Authorisation (ranging from 750 mg to 6 g per day) for at least two days, and actively breastfeeding.

- Breastfeeding must have commenced at least two weeks post-childbirth to ensure the collection of mature milk, and the infant must be at least four weeks old.
- Participants needed to be affiliated with the social security scheme or an equivalent and be able to understand and willing to sign a written Informed Consent document.

Exclusion criteria included infants born prematurely (i.e., gestational age less than 34 weeks), infants requiring specialised medical supervision or social worker support, mothers of twins, those with language barriers preventing effective communication, and patients under legal protection orders (curatorship or tutorship).

Results

Twenty-five breastfeeding mothers were enrolled in the study. Pharmacokinetic analysis of the plasma and milk samples was conducted using a validated LC-MS/MS method, in accordance with EMA/FDA standards.

Based on plasma and breast milk concentrations of amoxicillin, a population pharmacokinetic (PopPK) model was constructed using the MONOLIX software. The PopPK model allows us to describe the kinetic profile of amoxicillin in the plasma of breastfeeding mothers as well as its diffusion into breast milk, and the associated inter-individual variability. At this stage, none of the documented covariates (Tables I/II) explain, even partially, the observed variability. Using this model, we are currently conducting simulations of the quantities of amoxicillin that could be ingested by the breastfeeding newborn. Simultaneously, we are seeking to assess the potential impact of these quantities on the intestinal microbiota by simulations.

We monitored the occurrence of predefined adverse reactions in infants during breastfeeding, and no adverse reactions were reported (Table II). A decrease in breast milk production was also observed, though it was not linked to amoxicillin consumption (Table II).

Table I: Socio-demographic and clinico-biological data of the 25 breastfeeding mothers treated with amoxicillin.

Mother			
	mean	SD	CV(%)
Age (y)	35	4	11
Adverse events	0		
Frequency/day of breastfeeding	9	4	47
Decrease in milk production	n=5 mothers	no link with amoxicillin use	
Treatments other than amoxicillin	n=3 mothers with other drugs (n=1 with anti-hypertension - n=1 anti-inflammatory - n=1 antibiotics ; they are not the same mothers who experienced a decrease in milk production)		
Medical history	n=1 (hypertension)		
Alcohol	n=0		
Tabacco	n=0		
Weight (kg)	64.9	12.1	18.6
Height (cm)	164.5	5.9	3.6
Dose amoxicillin (mg)/day	2760	436	16
Frequency administration/day	2 x 1g/day: n=6 and 3 x 1g/day: n=19		

Table II: Socio-demographic and clinico-biological data of the 25 newborns from breastfeeding mothers treated with amoxicillin

Newborn			
Sex	n=12 males		
	n=13 females		
	mean	SD	CV(%)
Age (days)	166	148	89
Age (months)	5.5	4.9	89.0
Weight (kg)	6.7	2.7	40.2
Height (cm)	62.0	8.9	14.3
Adverse events	0		

The authors are in the process of preparing to publish the outcomes

Registration: EudraCT_2021-002247-30_Evaluation of **Amoxicillin** diffusion in breast milk according to population pharmacokinetic approach. CHU Toulouse, France

4.3 Levocetirizine/cetirizine

The aim of the Levocetirizine/cetirizine study was to quantify concentrations of cetirizine and levocetirizine in breast milk and to estimate drug exposure to infants. Breastfeeding women at least 8 weeks postpartum and using cetirizine or its pure (R)-enantiomer levocetirizine were eligible to participate.

Breast milk samples were collected at six predefined times during a dose interval (0, 2, 4, 8, 12 and 24 h after drug intake) at steady state. Infant drug exposure was estimated by calculating the absolute infant dose (AID) and the weight-adjusted relative infant dose (RID).

In total, 32 women were eligible for final inclusion, 31 women using cetirizine and one woman using levocetirizine. Means of the individual maximum and average cetirizine milk concentrations were 41.0 and 16.8 µg/L, respectively. Maximum concentrations occurred on average 2.4 h after intake, and the mean half-life in milk was 7.0 h. Estimated AID and RID for cetirizine in a day were 2.5 µg/kg and 1.9%, respectively. The corresponding values for levocetirizine were 1.1 µg/kg and 1.9%. No severe adverse events were reported.

The study demonstrated that the transfer of cetirizine and levocetirizine into breast milk is low and it is compatible with breastfeeding

Registration: EUPAS46213_Levocetirizine/cetirizine levels in human milk – an observational, clinical study among breastfeeding women. PharmaSafe, Pharmacoepidemiology and Drug Safety Research Group, Oslo, Norway.

The following publication has resulted from this research:

Transfer of cetirizine/levocetirizine into human breast milk and estimation of drug exposure to infants through breastfeeding: A human lactation study from the ConcePTION project. Nordeng H, Wegler C, Lindqvist A, Melander E, Magnusson M, Gandia P, Panchaud A, Baranczewski P, Spigset O. Basic Clin Pharmacol Toxicol. 2024 Jan;134(1):153-164.

4.4 Metformin

Transfer of metformin into human breast milk and the plasma of breastfeeding children - A low intervention trial with biobanking of breast milk and plasma in Västra Götalandsregionen and Region Örebro

The project had a low intervention trials design in the sense that breast milk and blood was to be collected merely to study excretion of metformin into breastmilk and transferal to her child. Participation in the study did not decide or in any other way interfere with patients' treatment as prescribed by their physician. Only patients that already had been assigned treatment with metformin by their physician will be approached and asked for participation.

Breast milk was collected at two times during the visit, using an electric breast milk pump. Venous blood was collected from the woman and from the infant. After centrifugation, plasma samples and breast milk sample were aliquoted, frozen at -80 degrees and stored at Biobank Väst and Örebro Biobank, respectively. When all samples had been collected, they were transferred to Uppsala Biobank. Samples were analysed for pharmacokinetic properties using mass spectrometry at the UDOPP Platform (Uppsala Drug Optimization and Pharmaceutical Profiling) at the Department of Pharmacy, Uppsala University.

The primary objective was to determine the concentration of metformin in plasma of breast-fed infants of lactating women treated for T2D. A secondary objective was to determine the milk-to-plasma ratio in the women, and based on absolute infant dose (AID) and dosage of mother the relative infant dose was calculated. The primary endpoint was the concentration of metformin in the breastfeeding child's plasma 4h after maternal dose intake. The secondary endpoint was the concentration of metformin in breast milk at 0h (trough) and 2h after intake. The tertiary endpoint was the maternal plasma concentration of metformin at 0h (trough) and 2h after intake. The measure of drug levels in plasma and milk, were carried out using a validated method consisting of high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS)

Figure 2. Overview of the metformin study sampling procedure

Sampling took place after development of mature milk, \approx six-eight weeks postpartum. The sampling took place after achieving a steady state; after having been on metformin without any dosage changes for a minimum of two weeks. All sampling took place the same day at the neonatal clinic in Göteborg, or at the breastfeeding clinic in Örebro. The mother brought her own metformin medications to the clinic.

Registration: EUPAS105190_Transfer of **Metformin** into human breast milk and the plasma of breastfeeding children - An observational cohort study with biobanking of breast milk and plasma in Västra Götalandsregionen Örebro. Uppsala University, Sweden.

4.5 Prednisolone

EU trial number: 2023508913-18-00 Title: Transfer of prednisolone to breast milk and blood plasma from breast-feeding children - A low-intervention study with biobanking of breast milk and blood plasma

Brief background: For many drugs today, there is a lack of sufficient evidence for how the drug can affect the child who breastfed. In many cases, this has meant that, for precautionary reasons, the drug is discontinued, or the mother is advised not to breastfeed. At the same time, the mother has the best benefit from the prescribed medicine, and it is known that breastfeeding is good for both the newborn and the mother. The purpose of the study was to investigate whether and how much prednisolone passes through breast milk to the child from mothers who have been prescribed the drug.

Primary objective: The primary objective was to determine the concentration of prednisolone in the plasma of breastfed infants of breastfed women treated with prednisolone to reduce inflammation. Secondary objective: Secondary objective was to determine prednisolone/prednisone concentration in breast milk and maternal plasma and maternal milk-to-plasma ratio and to calculate average daily infant dose (ADID) and relative infant dose (RID).

Primary Outcome Measure: The primary outcome measure was the concentration of prednisolone in the plasma of the nursing infant 2 hours after an infant is breastfed, with the feeding 1 hour after the maternal dose.

Secondary endpoint: The secondary endpoints were the concentration of prednisolone and prednisone in breast milk 1 hour after maternal dose intake and the maternal plasma concentration of prednisolone and prednisone 1 hour after prednisolone intake.

The study had a low-interventional design in the sense that breast milk and blood were collected solely to study the excretion of prednisolone. in the breast milk and transfer to the breastfed child.

EUPAS 100000059, CTIS 2023-508913-18-00

4.6 Venlafaxine

The venlafaxine demonstration study was built to analyse concentrations of venlafaxine and its active metabolite (o-desmethylvenlafaxine) in the breast milk of mothers with ongoing venlafaxine treatment, to allow the prediction of infant exposure through breast milk. This study was designed to have no impact on the therapeutic management of the patients, and no blood samples were taken from the mother or the child. The patients' enrolment was done through social media, selected websites directed towards pregnant and breastfeeding women and was coordinated by the CHUV. The informed consent was received in standard paper format and sent to the participant by post. Milk sampling was carried out by the participant with a breast pump. Sampling and infant health details were collected through telephone questionnaire by the investigators. Milk samples collected were sent to the milk biobank in Uppsala. The data was stored on the CHUV's secure server. All sampling and shipping instructions and study details were clearly explained to the participant.

Using a monocentric design chosen by WP4 members, we were able to enrol 2 patients taking venlafaxine while breastfeeding who provided 4 samples of breast milk each during an extended period of recruitment from 24 months. To be able to provide the urgently needed proof of concept studies using population Pharmacokinetic (popPK) to characterise infant exposure to venlafaxine as well as other SSRIs/SNRIs, we used/will use milk, maternal plasma and cord blood concentrations from a previous European study (SSRI-Milk study) to perform 3 popPK analysis.

The following publication has resulted from this research:

A population pharmacokinetic model for sertraline in women during the perinatal period - A contribution from the ConcePTION project. Monfort A, Cardoso E, Eap CB, Ansermot N, Crettol S, Fischer Fumeaux CJ, Graz MB, Harari MM, Weisskopf E, Gandia P, Allegaert K, Annaert P, Nordeng H, Hascoët JM, Claris O, Epiney M, Ferreira E, Leclair G, Csajka C, Panchaud A, Guidi M; collaborators of the SSRI Breast Milk study; *Br J Clin Pharmacol.* 2024 Jul 19. doi: 10.1111/bcp.16177. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 39030897.

The authors are in the process of preparing to publish the outcomes for the two topics mentioned below:

A population pharmacokinetic model for paroxetine in women during the perinatal period-A contribution from the ConcePTION project (ongoing)

A population pharmacokinetic model for venlafaxine in women during the perinatal period-A contribution from the ConcePTION project (ongoing)

Key lesson learned: A multicentric approach is essential for medications with low prevalence of use or those associated with a high level of stigma. Unicenter studies are feasible when the prevalence of medication use postpartum is high.

Medication with low prevalence of use or high stigma are challenging to study in isolation, a multicentric approach is crucial. When a medication is rarely used, collecting sufficient data from a single center can be difficult, but by combining data from multiple centers, researchers can gather larger and more representative samples, leading to more reliable and robust results. To ensure consistency across different centers, the use of standardized protocols becomes essential, as it guarantees that the data collected is comparable and reduces variability in the results. In the case of medications associated with stigma, patients may hesitate to participate in studies due to fear of judgment or discrimination. A multicentric approach can alleviate this concern by dispersing participation across various centers, making it easier for patients to contribute without drawing attention to a single location. Furthermore, pooling resources and expertise across multiple centers allows for better study designs, which are especially important when studying medications with limited use or stigma attached to them.

5. Standardised procedures for biobank sample analytics

Three bioanalysis methods using the liquid chromatography- mass spectrometry technique (LC-MS/MS) were developed and validated:

- 1) Method 1 - simultaneous quantification of cetirizine, venlafaxine, and O-desmethylvenlafaxine in human breast milk;
- 2) Method 2 - quantification of metformin in human breast milk and plasma; and
- 3) Method 3 - quantification of prednisolone in human breast milk and plasma.

The methods were optimised for high-throughput analysis in 96-well format, in which a small aliquot (40 μ L) of milk or plasma sample containing analytes were simply mixed with acetonitrile followed by centrifugation in a regular benchtop centrifuge (at 2465 \times g). The methods require minimal sample manipulation with simple acetonitrile protein precipitation. In addition, the methods quantified analytes at 4 – 20 times lower concentrations than in previous published bioanalytical methods. The total run time for the methods was up to 3 minutes.

These methods were validated for precision and accuracy, sensitivity, selectivity, matrix effects, extraction efficiency, and stability, in accordance with criteria set by FDA Guidance for Industry – Bioanalytical Method Validation 2018.

The methods provided are with the following sensitivity; analysing cetirizine at 0.39 μ g/L, venlafaxine at 0.28 μ g/L, O-desmethylvenlafaxine at 0.27 μ g/L, metformin at 0.65 μ g/L and prednisolone at 1.80 μ g/L in small volumes of breast milk and plasma in under 3 minutes.

The development and validation of methods 1 and 2, was described and published:

Simple and rapid quantification of cetirizine, venlafaxine, and O-desmethylvenlafaxine in human breast milk, and metformin in human milk and plasma with UHPLC-MS/MS; Wegler CH, Saleh A, Lindqvist A, Nordeng A, Smeraglia J, Baranczewski P, *Journal of Chromatography B*, 2022, 1205, 1-9.

6. Biobanking Guideline

If human biospecimens and associated data are collected for research, for example in the context of a clinical trial or a cohort, it is necessary that legal and regulatory requirements are followed. Furthermore, it is of utmost importance that the biospecimen collection and all subsequent process steps are carried out in a highly standardised way to fulfil pre-defined requirements and to satisfy - or even exceed – end-user expectations. To ensure this and thus provide high-quality biospecimens and associated data for research, it is essential that the respective study/cohort and/or the responsible biobank has all its processes clearly defined and under control. Only in this way it is possible to meet all the requirements and to sustainably maintain operations in the long term. This is best achieved if the study/cohort and/or biobank commits to and implements a quality management system (QMS). According to the ISO 9000 standard a QMS, among other things, “comprises activities by which the organisation identifies its objectives and determines the processes and resources required to achieve desired results”¹⁴. It is described as a dynamic system that is continuously improved and thus evolves. Quite often quality management (QM) activities are already taking place in an organisation, but they may not be subject to a formal system. To develop such a system, there are several international standards that can assist. The most relevant ones for biobanking are described in the following chapter 7.

7. Standards for the development and implementation of a QMS in biobanks

7.1 ISO 9001:2015 Quality Management System requirements

Generic guidance for the development of a basic QMS for any type of organisation is provided by the ISO 9001 standard which employs the process approach, considering the Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) cycle and the risk-based thinking approach. This enables the organisation to plan its processes and their interactions, to

adequately resource and manage its processes, and to identify and implement opportunities for improvement. It can also identify factors that could lead to process deviations and enable the organisation to take preventive measures¹⁵.

7.2 ISO 20387:2018 General requirements for biobanking

More specifically geared to the general requirements for competence, impartiality and consistent operation of biobanks including QC requirements and the requirements for the respective QMS is the ISO 20387 standard. It is “applicable to all organisations performing biobanking, including biobanking of biological material from multicellular organisms (e.g., human, animal, fungus and plant) and microorganisms for research and development”¹⁶.

The following sections include a short description of the requirements of the respective chapters of the ISO 20387 standard (Figure 3):

Figure 3: This figure shows the chapters of ISO 20387 General requirements for biobanking.

7.2.1 Introduction (ISO 20387 chapter 1):

The scope of the ISO 20387 standard specifies the general requirements for the competence, impartiality and consistent operation of biobanks including QC requirements to ensure that the biological material and data collections are of appropriate quality. Furthermore, it outlines for which organisations/purposes the document is applicable and that it can be used to confirm or recognise the competence of biobanks.

7.2.2 General requirements (ISO 20387 chapter 4):

The biobank shall have procedures in place for every biobanking process step for each type of biospecimen and the associated data. It is recommended to define the purpose of the respective biobank (e.g., mission and vision of the biobank). Furthermore, this chapter describes the concept of impartiality and confidentiality and how it can be applicable to the biobanking area according to the requirements of the standard. A biobank, whatever its purpose and whatever the nature of the samples it processes, should observe these principles in a manner appropriate to its specific characteristics.

7.2.3 Structural requirements (ISO 20387 chapter 5):

The biobank shall define the specifications of organisational, financial, governance and other structural components and has to explain them in more detail by creating a documented QMS accordingly. The scope of conformity with the standard, a risk-based approach and the strategic direction of the biobank are just a few elements within the QMS which need to be discussed and established to meet the requirements of the ISO 20387 standard.

7.2.4 Resource requirements (ISO 20387 chapter 6):

This chapter and its respective ISO subchapters 6.1- 6.5 deal with the general aspects of the necessary resources of the biobank: the personnel, facilities/dedicated areas and environmental conditions, externally provided processes, products and services and equipment. The biobank shall address its financial viability and safeguard it for its continuous activities. The personnel must act according to the confidentiality arrangements, they must be competent, and further personnel management activities have to be carried out. Considerations related to processes of safeguarding facilities and environmental conditions must be made (e.g., chemical safety, biosafety/biosecurity, physical safety, inventory protection, facility management, information/data security, fire safety etc., if applicable). All the externally provided processes, products, and services, which are being supplied by a legal entity (or part thereof) that is not the biobank, need to be reviewed for compliance with the biobank's requirements. The biobank shall have all the necessary equipment at its disposal. It shall take care of it and use it in a controlled way based on instructions.

7.2.5 Process requirements (ISO 20387 chapter 7):

All the relevant processes that occur during the life cycle of the biological material and its associated data in the biobank, including e.g., collection/acquisition, processing, storage, access, and distribution, needs to be defined and described.

Collection, reception and distribution, transport (internal/external), traceability, preparation and preservation, storage, retrieval, and QC of the biospecimens and associated data are key elements in the entire handling process. As these steps can take place at different clinical sites and/or laboratories, a description of the implemented standardised workflow is essential in order to guarantee the appropriate quality of samples for further analysis and/or for the intended use.

According to the standard validated and/or verified methods shall be used for critical activities, which need to be defined by the biobank, at all stages of the biospecimen life cycle to ensure fitness for the intended purpose.

Furthermore, the ISO 20387 subchapter 7.10 on management of information and data explains the requirements regarding the procedures for implementation, modification and use of computer systems, software, hardware, and database(s) when applicable.

The ISO 20387 subchapters 7.11 and 7.13 on nonconforming output and complaints relate to each other and define that procedures need to be in place for the management, the initiation of appropriate countermeasures and the required documented information in case the output doesn't comply with the predefined requirements of the biobank and/or agreement with the recipient/user, and/or agreement with the provider and received complaints.

The ISO 20387 subchapter 7.12 on report requirements describes the minimum information that the biobank must provide for its stakeholders and/or users.

7.2.6 Quality management system requirements (ISO 20387 chapter 8):

According to the standard it is required that a biobank establishes, documents, implements, and maintains a QMS which is capable of consistently achieving the requirements described in the standard and assure the quality of biobanking. For this purpose, either the requirements of the ISO 20387 chapters 8.2 to 8.9 (option A) must be fulfilled, or the biobank must already have established and maintains a QMS according to the ISO 9001 standard and fulfils the requirements of the ISO 20387 chapters 4-7 (option B).

The minimum a biobank QMS shall address is:

- Documented information for the QMS
- Control of QMS documents
- Control of records
- Actions to address risks and opportunities
- Improvement
- Corrective action for nonconforming outputs
- Internal audits
- Quality management reviews

A supportive document in the implementation of the quality management, management, and technical requirements of the ISO 20387 biobanking standard is the ISO/TR 22758:2020¹⁷. “It expands on aspects of ISO 20387 and provides examples for illustration purposes. The aim of this document is to assist biobanks to address competency of personnel and appropriate quality of biological material and data collections. This technical report is equally applicable to newly established and existing biobanks”.

As required by the ISO 20387 standard, all the relevant biobanking processes must be defined and described. Such a detailed description of the operational process steps is referred to as standard operating procedure (SOP). Biobank personnel should be trained on these SOPs and carry out the processes as described. Of course, the SOPs must correspond to the processes and procedures carried out on site, but templates can be a useful support for the initial creation of the documents. Some examples of template collections in the field of biobanking are:

- German Biobank Node: Handbook for quality management in biobanking. V3 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3403067
- SOPs, forms, and templates from the Swiss Biobanking Platform (free download from the Swiss Biobanking Platform website at <https://swissbiobanking.ch/documents/>)
- Manual of Biobank Quality Management (<https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-031-12559-1>)

8. Federated Biobank Network for breast milk research

The BBMRI-ERIC (Biobanking and BioMolecular resources Research Infrastructure - European Research Infrastructure Consortium) is a federated biobanking network that connects over 500 biobanks across Europe. It provides a robust platform for the exchange of information on high-quality biological samples and associated data, and for facilitating research in biomedical sciences. By standardising protocols, ensuring data interoperability, and adhering to strict ethical guidelines, BBMRI-ERIC enables researchers to access a diverse range of human samples, from tissue and blood to genetic material, enabling access to a diverse array of breast milk samples from various populations and geographic regions. This diversity is crucial for understanding how factors such as genetic variability, dietary habits, and environmental exposures influence the concentration of medications in breast milk and their subsequent effects on infants.

The BBMRI-ERIC Directory¹⁸ is an open catalogue for identifying biobanks and sample collections with potential samples and data available for further research use. It is possible to query using different already defined filters and free text search. When searching for e.g. breast milk, we can find three biobanks with breast milk sample collections available (see figure 4).

Figure 4. A free text search for "breast milk" in the BBMRI-ERIC Directory resulted in four breast milk collections being found from three biobanks, namely from CELSPAC Biobank in Czechia, Leipzig Medical Biobank in Germany, and Wroclaw Medical University Biobank in Poland.

The BBMRI-ERIC Directory offers a solution for sample collections with similar sampling objectives to form federated collection networks. Here the possibility to establish a federated sample collection network for the breast milk sample collections piloted in ConcePTION WP4 would be of great asset to researchers from academia and industry. The standardised breast milk sample collections utilising common SOPs on sample collection, in pre-analytical processes and in storing enable uniformity and high quality of the samples and data for subsequent analyses and research. The standardised sample collections contribute with greater impact to a better understanding of medicinal safety for pregnant and breastfeeding women and for their babies.

Ultimately, this also aligns with the key objective of the IMI Conception project - to establish a trusted ecosystem that can efficiently, systematically, and in an ethically responsible manner, generate and disseminate reliable evidence-based information regarding effects of medications used during pregnancy and breastfeeding to women and their healthcare providers. This will be achieved by generating, cataloguing, linking, collecting and analysing data from pharmacovigilance, modelling, routine healthcare, breastmilk samples through a large network¹⁹.

9. Conclusions

In this deliverable we established the standard documents for pre-examination processes in the context of handling of breast milk and blood sampling at the clinical site and at the participants' homes. The documents are developed to support further the sample handling processes in the five demonstration studies carried out in ConcePTION WP4. While collecting human biospecimen and related data for clinical research purpose, the ethical and regulatory requirements must be adhered to. Therefore, all the documents are compatible with requirements stemming from the guideline for Good Clinical Practice E6 (R2), as well as ICH-GCP for ensuring donor rights and safety. Furthermore, relevant European and International Standards for biobanking and pre-analytical sample handling were referred to improve the quality of the documentation; namely ISO 20378 General Requirements for Biobanking, ISO 9001 Quality Management System Requirements, and ISO 20186 series on Specifications for pre-examination processes for venous whole blood were used as a reference to identify requirements for the standard documentation.

The demonstration projects utilised the standardised documents developed in WP4 Task 4.4, specifically on measuring concentrations of the medicines of interest and their metabolites and assessing exposure of breastfed infants, among other things. Thus, the standardised documents' applicability and utility to the sample handling was confirmed. In the standardised documents we also offered general insights on biobanking to facilitate sample storing and management of breast milk and blood samples collected in the demonstration studies.

The standardised documents are an important resource to increase the quality of more rarer sample types, such as breast milk, and are therefore in key role when planning future projects on clinical studies. All the standardised documents and guidelines produced in this task will be made publicly available by BBMRI-ERIC to facilitate future prospective sample collections and research.

10. Repository for primary data

Demonstration studies: The data collected in the demonstration studies are stored in repositories in servers of the organisation conducting the study.

Standardised documents: No primary data to be deposited in a repository

11. References

¹ <https://catalogues.ema.europa.eu>

² https://encepp.europa.eu/index_en

³ <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/homepage>

⁴ <https://eudract.ema.europa.eu/index.html>

⁵ <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory-overview/research-development/compliance-research-development/good-clinical-practice>

⁶ Yeung *et al.* Enhancing translational research in paediatric rheumatology through standardization. *Nat. Rev. Rheumatol.* 2016;12:684-690. DOI: [10.1038/nrrheum.2016.156](https://doi.org/10.1038/nrrheum.2016.156)

⁷ Betsou *et al.* Standard PREanalytical Code Version 4.0. Biopreservation and Biobanking. 2024. DOI: [10.1089/bio.2024.0010](https://doi.org/10.1089/bio.2024.0010)

⁸ <https://www.spidia.eu/>

⁹ Dagher *et al.* Pre-analytical processes in medical diagnostics: New regulatory requirements and standards. *N Biotechnol.* 2019 Sep 25;52:121-125. doi: [10.1016/j.nbt.2019.05.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbt.2019.05.002). Epub 2019 May 15. DOI: [10.1016/j.nbt.2019.05.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbt.2019.05.002)

¹⁰ Riegman *et al.* How standardization of the pre-analytical phase of both research and diagnostic biomaterials can increase reproducibility of biomedical research and diagnostics. *N Biotechnol.* 2019;53:35-40. DOI: [10.1016/j.nbt.2019.06.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbt.2019.06.007)

¹¹ <https://www.iso.org>

¹² <https://www.cencenelec.eu>

¹³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reco/2023/498/oj>

- 14 ISO 9000:2015 Quality management systems – Fundamentals and vocabulary
- 15 ISO 9001:2015 Quality management systems – Requirements
- 16 ISO 20387:2018 Biotechnology – Biobanking – General requirements for biobanking
- 17 ISO/TR 22758:2020 Biobanking — Implementation guide for ISO 20387
- 18 <https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/>
- 19 <https://www.imi-conception.eu/background/description/>

12. Annexes of chapter 3.2

Annex 1 – Template_Providing Information_Home_V1.0

Information given to potential research participants collecting breast milk samples at home

Information to potential research participants concerning the study [Name of the study]

You are hereby asked if you would like to participate in the research study [Name of the study] and if you allow us to store any samples you provide for future research. This document gives you information about the study and what it means to participate.

What is the study about?

There is not enough knowledge about how much of the medications that a mother takes gets into her breast milk. ConcePTION is a public-private research project, funded by the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI2 JU) (<https://imi-conception.eu>), with the purpose to increase this knowledge about medications taken during pregnancy and breastfeeding. Within the project, breast milk and blood from mothers taking medication are collected, analyzed and stored in a biobank to enable medical research.

Within the research study [Name of study], we are now measuring how much of the medication [Name of medication] also called [tradenname/s] that gets into the breast milk. This will be compared with the intake [Applicable to studies also collecting blood:] and how much medication is in the mother's bloodstream. The results of the study will be reported at group level in scientific papers, without disclosing the identity of study participants. You are asked to participate in the study on [Name of medication] because you have visited [the participating clinical sites], are breastfeeding and at the same time using the medication, or plan to do so soon. The main person/organisation responsible for the study is [Name of organization].

What will happen if I decide to participate?

Participation means that you will express breast milk for us at [X] occasions and [Applicable to studies also collecting blood:] once let us draw blood. The time-points for sampling depends on when you take your medication. We will contact you to plan the sampling.

Breast milk sampling

When you collect breast milk, you express all the milk from one of your breasts, until it feels empty.

You express breast milk at home with the help of a breast pump you get to borrow from us. After gently inverting the expressed breast milk, you freeze a breast milk sample of 20 ml. You choose what to do with the remaining breast milk. When you express, you fill in and submit an [online-questionnaire and then are interviewed by phone] with the sampling time-point, the medication(s) you are using and when you have taken it/them, the condition or disease that you are treated for, details concerning how you went about sampling breast milk, age, ethnicity, your height, weight, and the age of your child². You store the samples of breast milk in your freezer at home until all samples have been collected. You will receive detailed instructions on how to collect the breast milk.

[Applicable to studies collecting blood:]

Blood sampling

You will have blood samples taken only at one time. Two tubes will be taken, together 15ml of your blood. If you already have a venous catheter and want us to use it to draw blood, additional 7,5 ml of blood will be drawn (this requires that the catheter has not previously been used to administer the medicine). When the blood sample is taken, you fill in and submit an [online-questionnaire/questionnaire/interviewed by phone].

You may not participate until two weeks after childbirth. A participation is estimated to take about [X] minutes.

Possible consequences and risks of participating in the study

[Applicable to studies also collecting blood:] When blood is collected, you usually feel a slight sting. You may get a bruise from it and there is always a small risk of nerve damage, which may be expressed as pain or numbness. You are not expected to benefit for the participants directly from participating.

What happens to my information?

The study will collect and save information about you. We will collect your contact information, information concerning the sampling time-points, the medication(s) you are using, when you have taken your medications, the condition/disease that you are treated for, details concerning breastfeeding and how you went about sampling breast milk, age, ethnicity, your height, weight, and the age of your child².

Your contact information will be stored at [X] to be able to contact you to plan the sampling. This contact information will be discarded when all information and samples have been collected.

The health-related information you provide will be labeled with a code and stored in a database at Uppsala University, Sweden. [Applicable if paper questionnaires are used: The paper questionnaires will be stored at [the local site] for ten years before it is discarded]. Your coded information will be transferred to a database at the University Medical Center in Utrecht, the Netherlands. Your health-related information will be saved for 10 years after the study has finished. Then it is discarded.

²If any additional data will be collected in the specific study, what data and how the data will be collected has to be described.

The blood and breast milk samples, information on the time-points of sampling and the handling of the samples will be sent to Uppsala Biobank in Sweden. This material will be labeled with a code. The code will be used to connect the samples you have provided with the information that is stored at the database at the University Medical Center in Utrecht but it will not be possible to link the code to you after the samples have been collected.

The purpose of the processing of your personal data is to investigate how much of [Name of the medication] that goes into breast milk and to be able to review the research afterwards. Your data will be processed in confidence and there is no access for unauthorized persons.

Responsible for your personal data is [X]. According to the EU General Data Protection Regulation, you have the right to know what information is stored about you in the study free of charge, and if necessary, to correct any errors. You can also request your data to be deleted or to restrict the processing of your data. If you would like to access the information, please contact [X]. The Data Protection Ombudsman at [X] may be reached at [X]. If you are dissatisfied with how your personal data is handled, you have the right to submit a complaint to the [X], which is the supervisory authority.

What will happen to my samples?

The collected blood and breast milk samples will be sent to [X] to prepare the samples for storage and later shipped and stored at Uppsala Biobank in Uppsala, Sweden (registration number 827 at the Swedish Health and Social Care Inspectorate). Responsible for the biobank are Region Uppsala and Uppsala University in Sweden. The levels of [Name of medication] in blood and breast milk will be analyzed at [UDOPP (Department of Pharmacology, Uppsala University)/ Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Toulouse] but may be sent abroad to another EU country for analysis. Your samples are used and saved for the purpose of this study for 10 years. Then they will be discarded unless you have consented to saving them for future research.

If you consent to saving your samples for future research, they will be made available for medical research purposes that are considered to be of benefit to society. At present, it is not possible to know what these specific purposes will be. It may refer to specific medical conditions or treatments, unknown diseases or genetic disorders. Genetic analyzes may be performed in which your entire genome (your DNA) may be determined. The samples will be made available for future medical research within the EU for an undetermined period of time. You decide if you want to make them available for public as well as commercial research.

You have the right to decline to saving the samples. If you consent to it, you have the right to later withdraw (undo) that consent. Then your samples will be discarded or de-identified. If you wish to withdraw your consent, please contact the Principal Investigator (PI) for the demonstration study [contact person at clinical site and contact information].

The samples may only be used in the manner you have consented to. Should there be any additional research that is not yet planned, an Ethical Review Board will decide if they can be used and if additional information needs to be communicated to the donor.

How do I get information about the results of the study?

You will not receive any individual results from the analyses of your samples. The results will be published in scientific journals. When this happens, it will be communicated on our website (<https://imi-conception.eu>).

Insurance and compensation

As a study participant, you are covered by a patient insurance through [X]. You will not receive any financial compensation for your participation.

Participation is voluntary

Your participation is voluntary and you can choose to cancel the participation at any time. If you choose to cancel your participation, you do not need to explain, nor will it affect your future care or treatment. If you want to cancel your participation, please contact the person responsible for the study (see below).

Contact information

If you have any questions about the study, please contact the research team:

[Principal Investigator for the demonstration study]

Contact person for sample collection]

Annex 2 – Template_Providing Information_Clinic_V1.0

Information given to potential research participants collecting breast milk samples at the clinical site

Information to potential research participants concerning the study [Name of the study]

You are hereby asked if you would like to participate in the research study [Name of the study] and if you allow us to store any samples you provide for future research. This document gives you information about the study and what it means to participate.

What is the study about?

There is not enough knowledge about how much of the medication/s that a mother takes gets into her breast milk. ConcePTION is a public-private research project, funded by the Innovative Medicines Initiative (<https://imi-conception.eu>), with the purpose to increase this knowledge about medication/s taken during pregnancy and breastfeeding. Within the project, breast milk and blood samples from mothers are collected, analyzed and stored in a biobank to enable medical research.

Within the research study [Name of study], we are now measuring how much of the medication [Name of medication] (also called [tradenname]) gets into the breast milk. This will be compared with the intake [Applicable to studies also collecting blood:] and how much medication is in the mother's bloodstream. The results of the study will be reported at group level in scientific papers, without disclosing the identity of study participants. You are asked to participate in the study on [Name of medication] because you have visited [the participating clinical sites], are breastfeeding and at the same are using medication, or plan to do so soon. The main responsible for the study is [Name of organization].

What will happen if I decide to participate?

Participation means that you will visit us at [Name of the clinic] to express breast milk at [X] occasions and [Applicable to studies also collecting blood:] once let us draw blood. The time-points for sampling depends on when you take your medication. We will contact you to plan the sampling.

Breast milk sampling

When you collect breast milk, you express all the milk from one of your breasts, until it feels empty. You express breast milk with the help of a breast pump you get to borrow from us. After gently inverting the expressed breast milk, we freeze a breast milk sample of 20 ml. You choose what to do with the remaining breast milk. When you express, you fill in and submit an [online-questionnaire/questionnaire/interviewed by phone] with the sampling time-point, the medication(s) you are using and when you have taken it, the condition or disease that you are treated for, details concerning how you went about sampling breast milk, age, ethnicity, your height, weight, and the age of your child³. You will receive detailed instructions on how to collect the breast milk.

[Applicable to studies collecting blood:]

Blood sampling

You will have blood samples taken once. Two tubes will be taken, together 15ml of blood. If you already have a venous catheter and want us to use it to draw blood, additional 7,5 ml of blood will be drawn (this requires that the catheter has not previously been used to administer the medicine). When the blood sample is taken, you fill in and submit an [online-questionnaire/questionnaire/interviewed by phone]

You may not participate until two weeks after childbirth. A participation is estimated to take about [X] minutes.

Possible consequences and risks of participating in the study

[Applicable to studies also collecting blood:] When blood is collected, you usually feel a slight sting. You may get a bruise from it and there is always a small risk of nerve damage, which may be expressed as pain or numbness. You are not expected to benefit directly from participating.

What happens to my information?

The study will collect and save information about you. We will collect your contact information, information concerning the sampling time-points, the medication(s) you are using, when you have taken your medications, the condition/disease that you are treated for, details concerning breast feeding and how you went about sampling breast milk, your age, ethnicity, height, weight, and the age of your child².

Your contact information will be stored at [X] in order to be able to contact you to plan the sampling. This contact information will be discarded when all information and samples have been collected.

The health-related information you provide will be labeled with a code and stored in a database at Uppsala University, Sweden. [Applicable if paper questionnaires are used: The paper questionnaires will be stored at [the local site] for ten years before it is discarded]. Your coded information will be transferred to a database at the University Medical Center in Utrecht, the Netherlands. Your health-related information will be saved for 10 years after the study has finished. Then it is discarded.

The blood and breast milk samples, information on the time-points of sampling and the handling of the samples will be sent to Uppsala Biobank in Sweden. This material will be labeled with a code. The code will be used to connect the samples you have provided with the information that is stored at the database at the University Medical Center in Utrecht but it will not be possible to link the code to you after the samples have been collected.

The purpose of the processing of your personal data is to investigate how much of [Name of the medication] goes into breast milk and to be able to review the research afterwards. Your data will be processed without access for unauthorized persons.

Responsible for your personal data is [X]. According to the EU General Data Protection Regulation, you have the right to know what information is stored about you in the study free of charge, and if necessary, to correct any errors. You can also request your data to be deleted or to restrict the processing of your data. If you would like to access the information, please contact [X]. The Data Protection Ombudsman at [X] may be reached at [X]. If you are dissatisfied with how your personal data is handled, you have the right to submit a complaint to the [X], which is the supervisory authority.

What will happen to my samples?

The collected blood and breast milk samples will be sent to [X] to prepare the samples for storage and later shipped and stored at Uppsala Biobank in Uppsala, Sweden (registration number 827 at the Swedish Health and Social Care Inspectorate). Responsible for the biobank are Region Uppsala and Uppsala University in Sweden. The levels of [Name of medication] in blood and breast milk will be analyzed at [UDOPP (Department of Pharmacology, Uppsala University)/ Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Toulouse] but may be sent abroad to another EU country for analysis. Your samples are used and saved for the purpose of this study for 10 years. Then they will be discarded unless you have consented to saving them for future research.

If you consent to saving your samples for future research, they will be made available for medical research purposes that are considered to be of benefit to society. At present, it is not possible to know what these specific purposes will be. It may refer to specific medical conditions or treatments, unknown diseases or genetic disorders. Genetic analyzes may be performed in which your entire genome (your DNA) may be determined. The samples will be made available for future medical research within the EU for an undetermined period of time. You decide if you want to make them available for public as well as commercial research.

You have the right to decline to saving the samples. If you consent to it, you have the right to later withdraw (undo) that consent. Then your samples will be discarded or de-identified. If you wish to withdraw your consent, please contact the PI for the demonstration study [contact person at clinical site and contact information].

The samples may only be used in the manner you have consented to. Should there be any additional research that is not yet planned, an Ethical Review Board will decide if they can be used and inform you.

How do I get information about the results of the study?

You will not receive the results from the analyses of your samples. The results will be published in scientific journals. When this happens, it will be communicated on our website (<https://imi-conception.eu>).

Insurance and compensation

As a study participant, you are covered by a patient insurance through [X]. You will not receive any financial compensation for your participation.

Participation is voluntary

Your participation is voluntary and you can choose to cancel the participation at any time. If you choose to cancel your participation, you do not need to explain, nor will it affect your future care or treatment. If you want to cancel your participation, please contact the person responsible for the study (see below).

Contact information

If you have any questions about the study, please contact us.

[Principal Investigator for the demonstration study]

[Name of R.N./Contact person for sample collection]

³If any additional data will be collected in the specific study, what data and how the data will be collected has to be described.

Annex 3 – Template_Consent Form_V1.0

Consent Form

Consent to participate in the research study [Name of study]

I have received oral and written information about the study and have had the opportunity to ask questions and get them answered. I get to keep the written information.

- I consent to participate in the research study "[Name of study]".
- I consent to having my information handled in the way described in the information.
- I consent to having my samples stored in a biobank as described in the information.

Place and date	Signature

Contact information (This information is used to contact you to plan the collection of [breast milk/blood and breast milk] samples. The information is discarded when the sampling is finished).

Name: _____

Address: _____

Phone: _____

E-mail: _____

Consent to saving samples for an undetermined time and use them for future broad medical research purposes

- I consent to having my blood [applicable only for studies collecting blood] and breast milk samples stored and saved for future medical research, of which the specific purposes have not been described here, as described in the patient information. If applicable, the research will first be reviewed and approved by an Ethical Review Board.

- I consent to having genetic analyses performed on the blood and breast milk samples.
- I consent to making the samples available for commercial medical research.

Place and date	Signature

Signature from the Care provider

- I confirm that I have given oral and written information about the study and that I have given the patient a copy of the patient information.

Place and date	Signature

Annex 4 – Template_Collection Milk_Clinic_V1.0

Procedures for collecting and processing breast milk samples

The following procedures describe the process of collecting breast milk samples from women that have consented to participate in the demonstration studies, and the process to prepare the samples for analysis. The procedures include the material and equipment needed. Procedures for collecting breast milk at the clinical site and at the participants' homes are presented separately. Uppsala Biobank provides the local labs with pre-labeled aliquot tubes.

Please note that the procedures have to be adapted to apply the specific conditions of the study and the local legislations and regulations. Details concerning the collection of breast milk are finally determined after the upcoming bioanalytical validation process.

Procedure for collecting and processing samples of breast milk at the clinical site

General Considerations

The breast milk sample collection is carried out by the mother at the clinical site. Sampling should take place after the development of mature milk (two weeks postpartum). The timing of the sampling in relation to medicine intake depends on the substance that is investigated. Sampling details and health-related details are collected using an online/paper questionnaire/by telephone.

Milk samples are put in the freezer at the clinical site and transferred to the local lab. If the lab does not have the capacity to do the aliquoting, the samples are stored locally and then sent to Uppsala Biobank, where the aliquoting is performed.

Material and Equipment

The material and equipment required for the participating woman to collect one sample of breast milk are:

- Electric breast pump (washed and sanitized according to the instructions). Preferably, all participants use pumps of the same brand and model.
- Instructions on how to assemble and sanitize the breast milk pump
- Milk study sampling kit:
 - One 100ml milk container labeled with the sample ID. The material should support -20C°, be compatible with the medicine, and able to be shipped without being damaged.
 - 1 small plastic bag
 - Sterile compresses
 - Sterile NaCl solution
 - Paper towels
 - 1 hand sanitizer
 - Soap
- [Applicable if information is collected using an online questionnaire:] A smartphone/tablet/computer with Android or iOS and Internet connection used for reporting sampling details and health information in an online-questionnaire.

- [Applicable if information is collected using an online questionnaire:] The web address to the online-questionnaire.
- [Applicable if information is collected using paper:] Paper questionnaire and pen.
- [Applicable if information is collected by telephone interviews:] Telephone
- Pleasant room temperature
- Convenient chair or any other furniture that enables a convenient sitting position while breast feeding
- Icepacks

Preparing for Breast Milk Samples

1. Decide together with the mother when she will visit the clinic for sampling.
2. [Applicable if information is collected by telephone interviews:] Decide when to perform the telephone interview to collect information (Annex 1). This has to be done the same day as the sample is taken.
3. The study contact person checks that the patient's identity corresponds to the informed consent and the assigned donor ID and the sample ID (printed on the label of the milk container).
4. The study contact person/personnel hands over the material to the participating woman
5. The participating woman is recommended to contact the study contacts person/personnel if she meets any problems when sampling. She should be able to quickly get assistance without having to leave the room while expressing milk.
6. Assemble the electric breast pump according to the instructions.

Breast Milk Sampling at the Clinical Site

1. Wash hands with water and soap and let them dry.
2. Disinfect hands with the hand sanitizer.
3. Wet the provided sterile compresses with the sterile NaCl solution and use it to wipe and clean one of your breasts, the breast you will be pumping from. Start with the nipple and then wipe in circles in a direction moving away from the nipple.
4. Use the breast pump according to the instruction manual provided by the manufacturer. Pump milk from the breast until it starts to feel empty. This usually takes about 10 to 20 minutes.
5. [Applicable if information is collected by questionnaires:] Continuously fill in the [online-questionnaire/questionnaire] while breast-feeding (Annex 1). If this is not possible, it is filled in afterwards, as soon as possible.
6. Disconnect the container provided with the breast pump.

The following steps can be conducted by the mother or personnel at the clinical site:

7. Invert the container 10 times to homogenize the milk.
8. Pour 20 ml of the breast milk in the provided 100ml study milk container labeled with the study donor ID and sample ID. If the full breast emptying yielded less than 20ml, pour this breast milk into the container. It is important that the container is not filled with more than 60ml as the milk expands when it is frozen. You decide what to do with the remaining milk.
9. Place the container in the plastic bag.
10. Hand the breast milk sample [and any paper questionnaire] to the study contacts person/personnel.

11. [Applicable if information is collected by questionnaires:] The participating woman makes sure that she has responded to all required information in the questionnaire [if online-questionnaire:] and submits it.

The following steps are performed by personnel at the clinical site:

12. The plastic bag with the container is put in the freezer and stored at -20 C°.
13. Sanitize the breast milk pump according to the instructions.
14. [Applicable if information is collected by telephone interviews:] The mother is called during the day to respond to the questions (Annex 1).
15. The milk is stored in a freezer until all samples have been collected and are then transported to the local lab (preferably) or Uppsala Biobank on dry ice.
16. The personnel submit the time-point of putting the sample in the freezer (Annex 2). [If paper questionnaires have been used:] The personnel submits the participant's responses to the paper questionnaire using the online-questionnaire (Annex 1).

Preparing the Samples for Analysis and Storage at the Local Lab or Uppsala Biobank

1. The sample is thawed and stirred gently.
2. The sample is aliquoted into the pre-labeled aliquot tubes leaving sufficient room in the tubes for liquid expansion during freezing. A maximum 20 ml of breast milk is aliquoted according to an algorithm developed during the validation process of the bioanalytics.
3. [Applicable if the aliquoting is performed at the local lab:] The samples are frozen at a temperature of -20C°.
4. The study donor ID, sampling time, sample ID, freezing time, and SPREC code for all aliquots are registered using an online-questionnaire.
5. The samples are shipped on dry ice to Uppsala Biobank. When samples are ready for shipment, please notify Uppsala Biobank by sending an e-mail to info@uppsalabiobank.uu.se (subject: ConcePTION: Sample shipment).
6. [Aliquots arriving/aliquoted] at Uppsala Biobank are frozen at a temperature of -80C°.

Annex 5 – Template_Collection Milk_Home_V1.0

Procedures for collecting and processing breast milk samples

The following procedures describe the process of collecting breast milk samples from women that have consented to participate in the demonstration studies, and the process to prepare the samples for analysis. The procedures include the material and equipment needed. Procedures for collecting breast milk at the clinical site and at the participants' homes are presented separately. Uppsala Biobank provides the local labs with pre-labeled aliquot tubes.

Please note that the procedures have to be adapted to apply the specific conditions of the study and the local legislations and regulations. Details concerning the collection of breast milk are finally determined after the upcoming bioanalytical validation process.

Procedure for collecting and processing samples of breast milk at the participant's home

General Considerations

The breast milk sample collection is carried out by the mother in her home. Sampling should take place after the development of mature milk (two weeks postpartum). The timing of the sampling in relation to medicine intake depends on the substance that is investigated. The milk samples are put in the freezer at the mother's home and are brought to the [local lab/clinical site] after the last sample has been collected. Sampling details and health-related information are reported by the mother using an online/paper questionnaire. The aliquoting is performed at the local lab. If the local lab does not have the capacity to do the aliquoting, the samples are stored locally and sent to Uppsala Biobank for aliquoting.

Material and Equipment

The material and equipment required for the participating woman to collect one sample of breast milk are:

- Electric breast pump (washed and sanitized according to the instructions). Preferably, all participants use pumps of the same brand and model.
- Instructions on how to assemble and sanitize the breast milk pump
- Milk study sampling kit:
 - One 100ml milk container labeled with the sample ID. The material should support -20C°, be compatible with the medicine, and able to be shipped without being damaged.
 - 1 small plastic bag
 - Sterile compresses
 - Sterile NaCl solution
 - Paper towels
 - 1 hand sanitizer
 - Soap
- [Applicable if information is collected using an online questionnaire:] A smartphone/tablet/computer with Android or iOS and Internet connection used for reporting sampling details and health information in an online-questionnaire.

- [Applicable if information is collected using an online questionnaire:] The web address to the online-questionnaire.
- [Applicable if information is collected using paper:] Paper questionnaire and pen.
- [Applicable if information is collected by telephone interviews:] Telephone
- Pleasant room temperature
- Convenient chair or any other furniture that enables a convenient sitting position while breast feeding
- A freezer
- Icepacks
- Shipping documents and material needed for transportation (according to local routines and any shipping company involved)
-

Preparing for Breast Milk Sampling

1. Decide together with the mother the time-points for sampling and when the samples will be transported to the local lab.
2. [Applicable if information is collected by telephone interviews:] Decide when to perform the telephone interview to collect information (Annex 1). This has to be done the same day as the sample is taken.
3. Order transportation if needed.
4. The study contacts person checks that the patient's identity corresponds to the informed consent and the assigned study donor ID and the sample ID (printed on the label of the milk container).
5. The study contacts person [hands over/sends] the material to the participating woman
6. The participating woman is recommended to contact the study contacts person if she meets any problems when sampling. She is provided a telephone number to quickly get assistance.
7. The woman assembles the electric breast pump according to the instructions.

Breast Milk Sampling at the Participant's Home

1. Wash hands with water and soap and let them dry.
2. Disinfect hands with the hand sanitizer.
3. Wet the provided sterile compresses with the sterile NaCl solution and use it to wipe and clean one of your breasts, the breast you will be pumping from. Start with the nipple and then wipe in circles in a direction moving away from the nipple.
4. Use the breast pump according to the instruction manual provided by the manufacturer. Pump milk from the breast until it starts to feel empty. This usually takes about 10 to 20 minutes.
5. Continuously fill in the [online-questionnaire/questionnaire] while breast-feeding (Annex 1). If this is not possible, it is filled in afterwards, as soon as possible.
6. Disconnect the container provided with the breast pump.
7. Invert the container 10 times to homogenize the milk.
8. Pour 20 ml of the breast milk in the provided 100ml study milk container labeled with the study donor ID and the sample ID. If the full breast emptying yielded less than 20ml, pour this breast milk into the container. It is important that the container is not filled with more than 60ml as the milk expands when it is frozen. You decide what to do with the remaining milk.
9. Place the container in the plastic bag
10. Put the plastic bag with the container in the freezer.
11. [Applicable if information is collected using questionnaires:] Make sure that you have responded to all required information in the questionnaire (Annex 1), including the time-point for putting the

sample in the freezer in the questionnaire.

12. [Applicable if information is collected using online-questionnaire:] Submit the questionnaire.
13. [Applicable if information is collected by telephone interviews:] The mother is called during the day to respond to the questions (Annex 1).
14. Sanitize the breast milk pump according to the instructions.
15. The milk is stored in the freezer until all samples have been collected.
16. The samples are transported on ice [If paper questionnaires are used: together with the questionnaires and breast milk pump] to the [local lab for aliquoting/clinical site for storage] using the ice packs, shipping material and shipping documents needed according to local routines.

Preparing the Samples for Analysis and Storage at the Local Lab or Uppsala Biobank

1. The sample is thawed and stirred gently.
2. The sample is aliquoted into the pre-labeled aliquot tubes leaving sufficient room in the tubes for liquid expansion during freezing. A maximum 20 ml of breast milk is aliquoted according to an algorithm developed during the validation process of the bioanalytics.
3. [Applicable if the aliquoting is performed at the local lab:] The samples are freezed at a temperature of -20C°.
4. The study donor ID, sampling time, sample ID, freezing time, and SPREC code for all aliquots are registered using an online-questionnaire.
5. The samples are shipped on ice to Uppsala Biobank. When samples are ready for shipment, please notify Uppsala Biobank by sending an e-mail to info@uppsalabiobank.uu.se (subject: ConcePTION: Sample shipment).
6. The aliquots are freezed at Uppsala Biobank at a temperature of -80C°.

Annex 6 – Template_Collection Blood_Clinic_V1.0

Procedures for Collecting and Processing Blood Samples

The following procedures describe processes of collecting blood samples from women that have consented to participate in the demonstration studies, and the processes of preparing the samples for analysis. The procedures include the materiel and equipment needed. Procedures for collecting blood at the clinical site and at the participants' homes are presented separately. To ease the burden on the mother, the blood samples are preferably taken in her home or during an appointment to the recruiting clinic.

Please note that the procedures have to be adapted to apply the specific conditions of the study and the local legislations and regulations. Details concerning the collection of blood are finally determined after the upcoming bioanalytical validation process.

1.1 Procedure for collecting and processing blood samples at the clinical site

General considerations

The blood drawings are carried out by trained personnel used to draw blood. The timing of the blood draw in relation to medicine intake and breast milk sampling depends on the specific study and substance being investigated. The tubes required depends on the specific study and if plasma or serum is being collected. A maximum time between drawing the blood to putting the aliquots in the freezer is decided based on the stability of the specific drug. Uppsala Biobank provides pre-labeled aliquot tubes.

Material and Equipment

The material and equipment required to collect blood are delivered with the Blood Sampling Kit provided by the study contacts person.

- Blood Sampling Kit:
 - 1 alcohol hand sanitizer
 - 1 pair of non-sterile gloves, in a well-fitting size
 - 1 tourniquet
 - Alcohol swabs for skin disinfection
 - 1 set of venipuncture equipment used at the local site. E.g., needle and a tube holder or a butterfly needle set.
 - [Applicable when plasma is collected:] Use 2 Li Hep tubes (à 7 ml) labeled with the study donor ID.
 - [Applicable when serum is collected:] Use two SST tubes (à 7 ml) labeled with study donor ID.
 - Cotton wool balls, compresses or similar materials used at the clinical site to stop bleeding.
 - Skin tape
 - One disposal unit
 - Extra material (gloves, swabs, venipuncture equipment, tubes, labels, compresses, and skin tape) in case the blood drawing fails.
 - [Applicable when an existing venous catheter is used to draw blood from:] One 7,5ml slush tube
 - [Applicable when an existing venous catheter is used to draw blood from:] The syringes, saline solution, heparin and catheter plugs necessary to flush and lock the catheter according to the local routines.

- [Applicable if information is collected using an online questionnaire:] A smartphone/tablet/computer with Android or iOS and Internet connection used for reporting sampling details and health information in an online-questionnaire.
- [Applicable if information is collected using an online questionnaire:] The web address to the online-questionnaire.
- [Applicable if information is collected using paper questionnaires:] Paper questionnaire and pen.
- [Applicable if information is collected by telephone interviews:] Telephone.
- Pleasant room temperature
- Convenient chair with armrests or any other furniture that enables a convenient sitting position with the arm relaxed.

Preparing for Blood Sampling

1. Decide together with the mother when she will visit the clinic for sampling.
2. [Applicable if information is collected by telephone interviews:] Decide when to perform the interview to collect information (Annex 3)
3. The study contacts person checks that the patient's identity corresponds to the informed consent and the assigned study donor ID (printed on the label of the blood tubes).

Blood Sampling at the Clinical Site

1. Prepare yourself and the required material and equipment according to the local routines. Make sure to have the material you need within an arm's reach.
2. Draw the blood in accordance with local routines and manufacturer instructions. Please note that existing venous catheters cannot be used if they have previously been used to administer [Name of medication]
3. [Applicable if existing venous catheters are used:] Make sure that a slush tube is filled completely before sampling, to avoid getting diluted samples.
4. [Applicable if information is collected using questionnaires:] Ask the woman to report sampling details and medicine intake (Annex 3) using the [paper questionnaire/online-questionnaire].
5. Respond to the online-questionnaire (Annex 4).
6. [Applicable if the participant responds to a paper questionnaire:] Submit her responses using the online-questionnaire.
7. The blood is transported to the local lab in a temperature that is consistent with the stability conditions.
8. [Applicable if information is collected by telephone interviews:] Information is collected by telephone interview afterwards, the same day as sampling (Annex 3)

Preparing the Samples for Analysis and Storage at the Local Lab

1. The LiHep tube is centrifuged at 2400g for 7 min.
2. Pipette the supernatant into aliquot tubes (à 225µl, pre-labeled with the sample ID). As many aliquot tubes as possible should be filled completely. However, no more than 8 aliquot tubes should be filled.
3. The study donor ID, sampling time, sample ID, freezing time, and SPREC code for all tubes are registered using an online-questionnaire.
4. The eight aliquots and the whole blood tube are frozen at -20C°.

5. The samples are shipped on dry ice to Uppsala Biobank. When samples are ready for shipment, please notify Uppsala Biobank by sending an e-mail to info@uppsalabiobank.uu.se (subject: ConcePTION: Sample shipment).
6. The aliquots and whole blood tube arriving at Uppsala Biobank are freezed at a temperature of -80C°.

Annex 7 – Template_Collection Blood_Home_V1.0

1. Procedures for Collecting and Processing Blood Samples

The following procedures describe processes of collecting blood samples from women that have consented to participate in the demonstration studies, and the processes of preparing the samples for analysis. The procedures include the material and equipment needed. Procedures for collecting blood at the clinical site and at the participants' homes are presented separately. To ease the burden on the mother, the blood samples are preferably taken in her home or during an appointment to the recruiting clinic.

Please note that the procedures have to be adapted to apply the specific conditions of the study and the local legislations and regulations. Details concerning the collection of blood are finally determined after the upcoming bioanalytical validation process.

1.1 Procedure for collecting and processing blood samples at the participant's home

General considerations

The blood drawings are carried out by trained personnel used to draw blood. The timing of the blood draw in relation to medicine intake and breast milk sampling depends on the specific study and substance being investigated. The tubes required depends on the specific study and if plasma or serum is being collected. The maximum time from drawing the blood to putting the aliquots in the freezer is decided based on the stability of the specific drug. Uppsala Biobank provides pre-labeled aliquot tubes.

Material and Equipment

The material and equipment required to collect blood are delivered with the Blood Sampling Kit provided by the study contacts person.

- Blood Sampling Kit:
 - 1 alcohol hand sanitizer
 - 1 pair of non-sterile gloves, in a well-fitting size
 - 1 tourniquet
 - Alcohol swabs for skin disinfection
 - 1 set of venepuncture equipment used at the local site. E.g., needle and a tube holder or a butterfly needle set.
 - [Applicable when plasma is collected:] Use 2 Li Hep tubes (à 7 ml) labeled with the study donor ID.
 - [Applicable when serum is collected:] Use two SST tubes (à 7 ml) labeled with study donor ID.
 - Cotton wool balls, compresses or similar materials used at the clinical site to stop bleeding.
 - Skin tape
 - One portable disposal unit
 - Extra material (gloves, swabs, venepuncture equipment, tubes, labels, compresses, and skin tape) in case the blood drawing fails.
 - [Applicable when an existing venous catheter is used to draw blood from:] One 7,5ml slush tube
 - [Applicable when an existing venous catheter is used to draw blood from:] The syringes, saline solution, heparin and catheter plugs necessary to flush and lock the catheter according to the local routines.
- [Applicable if information is collected using an online questionnaire:] A smartphone/tablet/computer with Android or iOS and Internet connection used for reporting sampling details and health information

in an online-questionnaire.

- [Applicable if information is collected using an online questionnaire:] The web address to the online-questionnaire.
- [Applicable if information is collected using paper questionnaires:] Paper questionnaire and pen.
- [Applicable if information is collected by telephone interviews:] Telephone
- Transportation equipment according to local routines.
- Pleasant room temperature
- Convenient chair with armrests or any other furniture that enables a convenient sitting position with the arm relaxed.

Preparing for Blood Sampling

1. Decide together with the mother when you will visit her to draw blood.
2. [Applicable if information is collected by telephone interviews:] Decide when to perform the interview to collect information (Annex 3)
3. Check that the patient's identity corresponds to the informed consent, the assigned study donor ID and the sample ID (printed on the label of the blood tubes).

Blood Sampling at the Participant's Home

1. Prepare yourself and the required material and equipment according to the local routines. Make sure to have the material you need within an arm's reach.
2. Draw the blood in accordance with local routines and manufacturer instructions. Please note that existing venous catheters cannot be used if they have previously been used to administer [Name of medication].
3. [Applicable if existing venous catheters are used:] Make sure that a slush tube is filled completely before sampling, to avoid getting diluted samples.
4. [Applicable if the participant responds to a paper questionnaire:] Ask the woman to report sampling details and medicine intake (Annex 3) using the [paper questionnaire/online-questionnaire].
5. Respond to the online questionnaire (Annex 4).
6. [Applicable if the participant responds to a paper questionnaire:] Submit her responses using the online-questionnaire
7. The blood is transported to the local lab in a temperature that is consistent with the stability conditions.
8. [Applicable if information is collected by telephone interviews:] Information is collected by telephone interview afterwards, the same day as sampling (Annex 3)

Preparing the Samples for Analysis and Storage at the Local Lab

1. The LiHep tube is centrifuged at 2400g for 7 min.
2. Pipette the supernatant into aliquot tubes (à 225µl, pre-labeled with the sample ID). As many aliquot tubes as possible should be filled completely. However, no more than 8 aliquot tubes should be filled.
3. The study donor ID, sampling time, sample ID, freezing time, and SPREC code for all aliquot tubes are registered using an online-questionnaire.
4. The eight aliquots and the whole blood second tube are frozen at -20C°.

5. The samples are shipped on dry ice to Uppsala Biobank. When samples are ready for shipment, please notify Uppsala Biobank by sending an e-mail to info@uppsalabiobank.uu.se (subject: ConcePTION: Sample shipment).
6. The aliquots and whole blood tube arriving at Uppsala Biobank are frozen at a temperature of -80C°.

Annex 8 – Template_ Questionnaire_ Breast Milk Sampling_Home_V1.0

[Questionnaire/Online-questionnaire] for mother to respond to when breast milk sampling

The first seven questions are only posed at the first breast milk sampling.

1. What is the age of your baby?

[Free text:] _____

2. At what gestational age was your baby born?

At ____ weeks and ____ days

3. What is your age?

____ years

4. What is your ethnicity?

[Free text:] _____

5. For what medical condition are you taking [Name of medication] (also called [tradenames])?

[Free text:] _____

6. What is your height?

____ cm

7. What is your current weight?

____ kg

8. What medications are you taking?

[Free text:] _____

9. Are you using any traditional medicinal products?

No Yes, I use the following: [Free text:] _____

10. What dose of [Name of medication] (also called [tradenames]) do you take?

[Free text:] _____ I do not know

11. How often do you take [Name of medication] (also called [tradenames])?

[Free text:] _____

12. Please indicate when you took your last dose of your medication.

Date: ___/___/___ ex. 20/01/2012 time: _____ h _____ ex. 12h52

13. Please indicate if you recall missing a dose during the last [7 days/other appropriate time interval]

I have not missed a dose during that time I am not sure [Should be adjusted to the specific medication studied:] yes, _____ days ago at _____ h _____ ex. 12h52 PM or AM

14. Please indicate when your last breastfeeding occurred

Date: ___/___/___ ex. 20/01/2012 time: _____ h _____ ex. 12h52

15. At what time did you begin pumping breast milk?

Date: ___/___/___ ex. 20/01/2012 time: _____ h _____ ex. 12h52

16. Where did you take the breast milk sample from?

left breast right breast

17. Time of removal?

- before breastfeeding
- immediately after breastfeeding
- breastfeed left side right side both sides
- Combination of both (sample was partially taken before and after breastfeeding)
- breastfeed left side right side both sides

18. Have you [frozen the breast milk sample/given the breast milk sample to the personnel]?

- Yes, at Date: ____/____/____ ex. 20/01/2012 time: _____ h _____ ex. 12h52

Annex 9 – Template_ Questionnaire_ Breast Milk Sampling_ Clinic_ V1.0

Online-questionnaire for personnel to respond to when breast milk sampling has been performed at the clinical site

The first seven questions are only posed at the first breast milk sampling.

1. What is the age of your baby?

[Free text:] _____

2. At what gestational age was your baby born?

At _____ weeks and _____ days

3. What is your age?

_____ years

4. What is your ethnicity?

[Free text:] _____

5. For what medical condition are you taking [Name of medication] (also called [tradenames])?

[Free text:] _____

6. What is your height?

_____ cm

7. What is your current weight?

_____ kg

8. What medications are you taking?

[Free text:] _____

9. Are you using any traditional medicinal products?

No Yes, I use the following: [Free text:] _____

10. What dose of [Name of medication] (also called [tradenames]) do you take?

[Free text:] _____ I do not know

11. How often do you take [Name of medication] (also called [tradenames])?

[Free text:] _____

12. Please indicate when you took your last dose of your medication.

Date: ____/____/____ ex. 20/01/2012 time: _____ h _____ ex. 12h52

13. Please indicate if you recall missing a dose during the last [7 days/other appropriate time interval]

I have not missed a dose during that time I am not sure [Should be adjusted to the specific medication studied:] yes, ____ days ago at ____ h ____ ex. 12h52 PM or AM

14. Please indicate when your last breastfeeding occurred

Date: ____/____/____ ex. 20/01/2012 time: _____ h _____ ex. 12h52

15. At what time did you begin pumping breast milk?

Date: ____/____/____ ex. 20/01/2012 time: _____ h _____ ex. 12h52

16. Where did you take the breast milk sample from?

left breast right breast

17. Time of removal?

- before breastfeeding

- immediately after breastfeeding
- breastfeed left side right side both sides

- Combination of both (sample was partially taken before and after breastfeeding)
- breastfeed left side right side both sides

18. Has the breast milk sample been frozen?

- Yes, at Date: ___/___/___ ex. 20/01/2012 time: _____ h _____ ex. 12h52

Annex 10 – Template_Questionnaire_Blood Sampling Mother_V1

[Questionnaire/Online-questionnaire] for mother to respond at blood sampling

1. What medications are you taking?

[Free text:] _____

2. Are you using any traditional medicinal products?

No Yes, I use the following: [Free text:] _____

3. What dose of [Name of medication] (also called [tradenames]) do you take?

[Free text:] _____ I do not know

4. How often do you take [Name of medication] (also called [tradenames])?

[Free text:] _____

5. Please indicate when you took your last dose of your medication.

Date: ___/___/___ ex. 20/01/2012 time: _____ h _____ ex. 12h52

6. Please indicate if you recall missing a dose during the last [7 days/other appropriate time interval]

I have not missed a dose during that time

I am not sure

[Should be adjusted to the specific medication studied:]

yes, ___ days ago at ___ h ___ ex. 12h52 PM or AM

7. Please indicate when your last breastfeeding occurred.

Date: ___/___/___ ex. 20/01/2012 time: _____ h _____ ex. 12h52

Annex 11 – Template_Questionnaire_Blood Sampling Personnel_V1.0

Online-questionnaire for personnel to respond to after blood sampling

1. When was the blood sample drawn?

Date: ___/___/___ ex. 20/01/2012 time: _____ h _____ ex. 12h52

2. Where did you take the blood sample from?

left arm right arm both sides Other location: _____

3. How was the blood drawn?

- By puncturing the skin
- From a peripheral venous catheter
- From a port-à-cath
- From a PICC-line
- From another catheter: _____

4. What type of tube was used? _____

5. What type of venepuncture equipment was used? _____

Annex 12 – Work Instruction_Sample_Shipment_V1.0

Uppsala Biobank

Work Instruction – Sample shipment

Purpose

This Work Instruction (WI) describes the procedure of shipping biobank samples to Uppsala Biobank within the ConcePTION study, including transfer of sample data.

Procedure

All collected samples are labelled with labels provided by Uppsala Biobank to the local site.

When all the study samples of a donor have been collected, the samples and their associated sample data shall be shipped and transferred to Uppsala Biobank for long time storage. This will be done in two steps – transfer of sample data and shipping of samples.

1) Transfer of sample data

Before the samples can be shipped to Uppsala Biobank, the data associated to the samples must be transferred and approved by Uppsala Biobank.

The sample data needs to be transferred in a predetermined format which includes study donor ID, sampled date and time, label ID (see Attachment 1_ConcePTION template, instructions in comments). The sample data file is generated by the site and transferred to Uppsala Biobank in an encrypted format (see WI Sending encrypted data). The sample data will be introduced into the Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS) of Uppsala Biobank.

2) Shipping of samples

Inform Uppsala Biobank of the planned sample shipment by sending an email info@uppsalabiobank.uu.se. An approval of the sample shipment is needed before the samples can be shipped. The tracking number of the shipment is communicated to Uppsala Biobank when the shipment is being scheduled.

The samples can only be shipped three or more days before weekends or Swedish bank holidays. The shipment can be done using the courier companies DHL or FedEx.

The local site needs to have a user account by the intended courier company and refer the cost of the shipment to the account of Uppsala Biobank (DHL xxxxxxxxx or FedEx xxxxxxxxx).

The samples will be shipped frozen with ice packs (~-20°C) to Uppsala Biobank. The local site needs to ensure that the shipping procedure is handled according to IATA rules and national guidelines, including the packing of samples, HS code and commercial invoice. Uppsala Biobank requires the samples to be packed with double envelopes, containing an adsorption material in the first container. The shipment should be marked "Exempt human specimen".

Delivery address:

Uppsala Biobank / UCR Lab
Dag Hammarskjölds väg 38, plan 5
785 51 Uppsala
SWEDEN

Name Surname

name.surname@ucr.uu.se

+46 18 xxx xx xx

Sample receipt

Uppsala Biobank will confirm the receipt of samples by reply on the email sent (see 2, above) to the local site.

Annex 13 – Work Instruction_Sending_Encrypted_Data_V1.0

Uppsala **Biobank**

Work Instruction – Sending encrypted data

Purpose

This Work Instruction (WI) describes the procedure of transferring encrypted data to Uppsala Biobank within the ConcePTION study.

Procedure

Uppsala Biobank uses the program FileShare (<https://fileshare.ucr.uu.se/>) to send and receive files encrypted.

1. The first time FileShare is used, contact information needs to be stated and verified to the program (a code sent to the e-mail address stated).
2. To transfer data - choose "Provide".
3. Add name.surname@ucr.uu.se to "Recipients" and press "Next".
4. Under "Add Files", add the sample data file and press "Next".
5. Choose one of the two checkboxes "Generate password" or "Enter password". Note the password and press "Next". If possible, use the same password every time sample data is transferred from the local site to Uppsala Biobank.
6. Press "Start transfer".
7. Text the password from above (5) to +46 xx xxx xx xx.
8. Uppsala Biobank will check the transferred data and approval or disapprove the data transfer by email.

Annex 14 – Work Instruction_Sample_Storage_V1.0

Uppsala **Biobank**

Work Instruction – Sample storage

Purpose

This Work Instruction (WI) describes the procedure of how the biobank samples of the ConcePTION study are stored at Uppsala Biobank.

Sample storage

The samples are stored at the storage facility of Uppsala Biobank. The samples are stored in -80°C freezers connected to temperature alarms. If the temperature rises above -60°C, an alarm goes to the facility operation team at the University Hospital that monitors and acts on alarms 24/7. If a freezer fails to lower the temperature, the facility operation team moves the samples to a back-up freezer.

LIMS

Sample information related to the physical sample is transferred to the Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS) of Uppsala Biobank according to WI Sample shipment. LIMS also tracks the position and handling of the samples at Uppsala Biobank.

Withdrawals

Uppsala Biobank is the custodian of the ConcePTION sample collection. Withdrawals from the ConcePTION sample collection have to be approved by a ConcePTION Governance Board. After approval, Uppsala Biobank will handle samples for withdrawal.